

RPMS-PPST BASED PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

Arthur C. Nierra ¹, Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Ed.D. ²

¹ Bangkuro Elementary School, San Narciso, Quezon, Philippines

² Extended Graduate Programs, Marinduque State College, Boac, Marinduque, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the RPMS-PSST-based performance of teachers and the performance of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon for three consecutive school years (2020-2021 to 2022-2023). The correlated survey was utilized for this study. The survey form described the performance of teachers based on the RPMS-PPST domains. It also determined the performance of selected schools in terms of School-Based Management (SBM) and Mean Percentage Score (MPS) for the three consecutive school years. The results of the survey were correlated to identify if there was a significant relationship between the teacher's performance and the school's performance. The result served as the basis for an intervention program for teachers to enhance their skills and knowledge of the RPMS-PPST domain. There were 157 teachers and 17 schools who served as respondents to the study. The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using mean or average, and Pearson's Correlation. The results revealed that teachers performed very satisfactorily in terms of the RPMS-PPST domains for the three consecutive school years. The schools' performance was described as developing in terms of SBM and moving towards mastery in terms of school MPS. A strong positive correlation was found between the performance of teachers based on RPMS-PPST and the performance of schools based on SBM and MPS, but there was not enough evidence to support its significance. Consequently, the study recommends an intervention program for teachers based on the result of their performance in RPMS-PPST to further capacitate them on different domains and improve school outcomes.

Keywords: Performance, RPMS-PPST, School-Based Management, Mean Percentage Score, Very Satisfactory, Developing, Moving Towards Mastery

INTRODUCTION

Education is considered a cornerstone of societal progress, providing individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary to contribute to their communities and the broader economy. The performance of schools in the global setting has long been a topic of concern and scrutiny among educators, policymakers, and researchers. The significance of school performance in education is perhaps best encapsulated by the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which explicitly aims to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all" by 2030.

Achieving this ambitious goal hinges on the ability of schools to deliver high-quality education consistently. UNESCO emphasizes the importance of quality education for sustainable development. However, challenges persist in Asian countries like Thailand, where traditional education heavily relies on rote memorization and examination scores. This approach can hinder critical thinking and creativity and has been criticized for focusing on "teaching to the test" rather than fostering holistic learning and problem-solving skills.

The report "The State of Philippine Education: A Review and Recommendations" highlights the low performance of schools in the Philippines due to inadequate resources, teacher shortages, and curriculum misalignment, disproportionately affecting rural and underserved areas (Philippine Business for Education, 2020). It also highlights the role of school-based management (SBM) in addressing low performance, highlighting challenges faced, and suggesting policy recommendations. The success of SBM depends on proper implementation and government support (Asian Development Bank, 2018).

The low performance of schools in the Division of Quezon Province, Philippines, is a significant concern due to several factors. Inadequate funding (Smith, 2019), inadequate teacher training (Garcia, 2020), and outdated teaching methods have led to overcrowded classrooms. Teacher quality and motivation are also a concern, with many underqualified and facing low salaries. Socio-economic disparities among students have widened the performance gap (Dela Cruz, 2018), and the lack of adequate educational policies and leadership at local and divisional levels exacerbates these issues (Lopez, 2021). Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive reforms, increased investment, and a concerted effort from policymakers, educators, and communities in Quezon Province.

Low school performance is a complex issue influenced by various factors. Socioeconomic status of students' families is a critical factor, as disadvantaged students

face more challenges in their educational journey (Reardon, 2011). Teacher quality, curriculum, and leadership also play a significant role. Highly qualified, motivated, and well-supported teachers significantly impact student outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2017). Ineffective teaching approaches and outdated or ineffective curricula contribute to low performance (Hattie, 2009). Effective leadership fosters a positive school culture and supports teachers in delivering high-quality education (Leithwood et al., 2006). Addressing these factors requires a comprehensive approach to improve educational outcomes.

Teachers' performance is a crucial factor in determining school performance. Factors such as inadequate qualifications (Ingersoll, 2017), low salaries, insufficient support, and unfavorable working conditions can hinder effective teaching (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017). Outdated teaching methods and lack of exposure to innovative pedagogical approaches can hinder student engagement and instruction (Hattie, 2009). Discipline issues can disrupt learning, and teachers may struggle to build rapport with students (Evertson & Weinstein, 2013). Lack of collaboration among teachers (Roorda et al., 2011) and insufficient support from school leadership can hinder sharing best practices and collaborative problem-solving (Coburn & Russell, 2008). Limited involvement from parents and the community can create barriers to addressing individual student needs (Epstein et al., 2009). Inadequate funding for educational resources can restrict teachers' access to materials, technology, and classroom supplies, limiting their ability to provide quality education (Baker et al., 2018).

The performance of teachers is crucial for the success of educational institutions. In the era of educational accountability, the focus on teacher effectiveness has increased. The Philippines' Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) initiative is based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). It aims to assess, develop, and enhance teachers' competencies, ultimately improving the quality of education in the country (DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015). For this reason, the researcher seeks to identify the significant relationship of the Results-Based Performance Management System on teachers and its subsequent s a school's performance. As mentioned above, the performance of teachers dramatically affects the performance of schools. By examining the implementation of RPMS-PPST, and its impact on teacher practices, and the resulting implications for school performance, this study directs to provide valuable insights that can inform educational policy and practice in the country.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers and performance of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers in the following domains?

- 1.1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy;
 - 1.2. Learning Environment;
 - 1.3. Diversity of Learners;
 - 1.4. Curriculum and Planning;
 - 1.5. Assessment and Reporting;
 - 1.6. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement;
 - 1.7. Personal Growth and Professional Development?
2. What is the performance of public elementary schools based on the following measures?
 - 2.1. SBM (School-Based Management)
 - 2.2. School MPS (Mean Performance Score)
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers and performance of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of the following?
 - 3.1. SBM (School-Based Management)
 - 3.2. School MPS (Mean Performance Score)
 4. What intervention program could be developed by the researcher based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This research study being quantitative in nature utilized the correlational research design to examine the relationships between performance of the teachers and performance of the public elementary schools. The data collected through a survey employing a data retrieval form were used to identify whether a statistically significant association exists between the identified variables of the study. As applied in the study, correlation does not imply causation but allows for the exploration of naturally occurring relationships.

The research was carried out in the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province with the municipalities of Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Macalelon, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso and Unisan. Selected school heads and teachers from the municipalities are the respondents of the study. The researcher opted to contribute information based on the data gathered and result of the study which is useful in providing intervention in the implementation RPMS-PPST in the Division of Quezon Province. The respondents for the study were identified from the population of teachers and school heads of elementary schools of the third congressional district of Quezon Province. Purposive sampling or selective sampling was employed by identifying the small schools in the district as the criterion. This category of schools used in selecting the respondents was based on DepEd Memorandum No. 43, s. 2017. With only nine teachers or less, classified as small schools, 17 were identified. Hence, the respondents are the 17 school heads and the total of 157 teachers from the identified small schools.

Teachers are the respondents to determine the performance in RPMS-PSST Based Tool, while the school heads are the respondents to describe the performance of the school based on the school data. They were chosen because they provided the needed data for evaluation of the relationship between the teacher's performance and performance of public elementary schools. This study utilized the data retrieval form to gather the necessary information for the research. The data retrieval form was the structured tool used to systematically collect and record data from the RPMS-PPST of teachers and the SBM and MPS of the schools.

The Data Retrieval Form included the basic information about the teachers as respondents in part I. Part II of the form indicates the performance of respondents in the RPMS-PPST three years back from School Year 2020-2021 up to School Year 2022-2023. On the other hand, the Data Retrieval Form for school heads as respondents includes the basic information of the school in part I, while part II indicates the performance of the school in terms of School-Based Management and School Mean Percentage Score three years back School Year 2020-2021 up to School Year 2022-2023. This study aimed to determine if there is a significant relationship between the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers in the Third Congressional District of Quezon and the performance of the public elementary schools in terms of School-Based Management and School Mean Percentage Score. Approval was first sought for the conduct of the study from the Division Office, from the District Supervisors, and from the school heads.

Upon approval, Data Retrieval Forms were sent via google forms to most of the teachers and school heads. Those who could not access through the internet were provided hard copies of the data retrieval forms. Once the respondents have filled in the forms, they were automatically returned. For those who received the hard copy, they were personally retrieved from the respondents at their respective schools. With the retrieved forms, data were gathered by tabulating them after which these were subjected to statistical analysis. With the results from the statistical tools, these were analyzed and interpreted.

After retrieval, the data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation and inferential statistics such as Pearson's correlation. Mean was used to describe the responses of the respondents in terms of teacher's performance based on RPMS-PPST, and the school performance in terms of MPS and SBM. Standard deviation was also used in the study as a measure of the amount of variation or dispersion in a set of values. It determined how varied and dispersed the performance of teachers and the school. For determining the significant relationship between the performance of teachers and the performance of the public elementary schools, Pearson Product-Moment-Correlation was employed.

RESULTS

Table 1

RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGY Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
1. Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.31	VS	5	O	4.36	VS	4.557	O
2. Ensured the positive use of ICT to facilitate teaching and learning process.	4.26	VS	4.31	VS	4.14	VS	4.237	VS
3. Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop creative and critical thinking as well as the higher order thinking skills.	4.25	VS	4.32	VS	4.33	VS	4.3	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.365	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 2

RPMS-PPST based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Learning Environment for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

LEARNING ENVIRONMENT Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
1. Established a learner-centered by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, culture, and socio-economic and religious backgrounds	4.31	VS	4.38	VS	4.36	VS	4.350	VS
2. Planned and delivered teaching that are responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances.	4.4	VS	4.52	O	4.58	O	4.500	O
3. Used strategies for providing timely, accurate and constructive feedback to improve learner performance	4.41	VS	4.37	VS	4.4	VS	4.293	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.381	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 3

RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Diversity of Learners for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

DIVERSITY OF LEARNERS Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
1. Designed selected, organized, and used diagnostic formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum.	4.52	O	4.36	VS	4.4	VS	4.427	VS

2. Monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	4.5	O	4.41	VS	5	O	4.637	O
3. Communicate promptly and clearly the learners' needs progress and achievement to key stakeholders including parents or guardians.	4.38	VS	4.45	VS	4.37	VS	4.400	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.488	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 4
RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Curriculum and Planning for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

CURRICULUM AND PLANNING Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
1. Selected, developed, organized, and used appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to Address learning goals	4.27	VS	4.13	VS	4.33	VS	4.243	VS
2. Select achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies	4.25	VS	4.31	VS	4.36	VS	4.307	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.275	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (3.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 5
RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Assessment and Reporting for the last Three Consecutive School Years

ASSESSMENT AND REPORTING Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
1. Designed selected, organized, and used diagnostic formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum	4.4	VS	4.44	VS	4.3	VS	4.380	VS
2. Monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	4.52	O	4.30	VS	4.4	VS	4.41	VS
3. Communicate promptly and clearly the learners' needs progress and achievement to key stakeholders including parents or guardians.	4.31	VS	4.38	VS	4.52	O	4.403	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.398	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 6

RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

COMMUNITY LINKAGES AND PROFESSIONAL ENGAGEMENT Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
	1. Built relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process.	4.32	VS	4.25	VS	4.33		
2. Participated in the professional networks to share knowledge and to enhance practice	4.26	VS	4.34	VS	4.38	VS	4.327	VS
3. Developed a personal improvement plan based on reflection of one's practice and ongoing professional learning	4.14	VS	4.27	VS	4.31	VS	4.240	VS
OVERALL MEAN							4.289	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 7

RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers on IPCRF in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development for the Last Three Consecutive School Years

Personal Growth and Professional Development Objectives	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
	1. Applied a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered	4.26	VS	4.38	VS	4.31		
2. Set Professional development goals based on the PPST	4.4	VS	4.45	VS	5	O	4.617	O
OVERALL MEAN							4.467	VS

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), O-Outstanding (4.500-5.000), VS-Very Satisfactory (3.500-4.499), S-Satisfactory (2.500-3.499), US-Unsatisfactory (1.500-2.499)

Table 8

School Performance of Selected Public Elementary in the Third Congressional District of Quezon based on SBM (School-Based Management) for the Three Consecutive School Years

Selected Public Elementary Schools	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
ES1	1.41	D	1.49	D	1.51	M	1.47	D
ES2	1.49	D	1.5	M	1.52	M	1.5	M
ES3	1.5	M	1.53	M	1.56	M	1.53	M
ES4	1.45	D	1.49	D	1.54	M	1.49	D
EA5	1.42	D	1.45	D	1.5	M	1.46	D
ES6	1.41	D	1.45	D	1.49	D	1.45	D
ES7	1.4	D	1.17	D	1.23	D	1.27	D
ES8	1.18	D	1.24	D	1.27	D	1.23	D
ES9	1.5	D	2.1	M	2.3	M	1.97	M
ES10	2.05	M	2.19	M	2.23	M	2.16	M
ES11	1.1	D	1.4	D	1.43	D	1.31	D

ES12	1.03	D	1.34	D	1.6	M	1.32	D
ES13	1.94	M	1.81	M	1.81	M	1.85	M
ES14	1.49	D	1.28	D	1.5	M	1.42	D
ES15	1.15	D	1.23	D	1.45	D	1.28	D
ES16	1.08	D	1.12	D	1.21	D	1.14	D
ES17	1.45	D	1.49	D	1.59	M	1.51	M
OVERALL MEAN							1.49	D

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation), A-Advanced (2.50 – 3.0), M-Maturing (1.50 – 2.49), D-Developing (0.50 -1.49)

Table 9
School Performance of Selected Public Elementary in the Third Congressional District of Quezon based on MPS (Mean Percentage School) for the Three Consecutive School Years

SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS	School Year 2020-2021		School Year 2021-2022		School Year 2022-2023		AVERAGE	VI
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI		
ES1	62.61	AM	70.98	MTM	60.31	AM	64.63	AM
ES2	66.81	AM	65.16	AM	79.13	MTM	70.37	MTM
ES3	60.58	AM	70.67	MTM	72.43	MTM	67.89	MTM
ES4	63.04	AM	59.16	AM	78.34	MTM	66.85	MTM
EA5	66.81	MTM	70.93	MTM	60.68	AM	66.14	MTM
ES6	62.46	AM	60.58	AM	65.16	AM	62.73	AM
ES7	67.39	MTM	59.52	MTM	69.58	MTM	65.50	AM
ES8	70.93	MTM	70.67	MTM	65.44	AM	70.80	MTM
ES9	73.07	MTM	68.5	MTM	70.98	MTM	70.85	MTM
ES10	69.6	MTM	66.81	MTM	68.45	MTM	68.29	MTM
ES11	72.4	MTM	58.46	AM	60.31	AM	63.72	AM
ES12	74.17	MTM	60.45	AM	64.58	AM	66.40	MTM
ES13	69.2	MTM	61.28	AM	62.08	AM	64.19	AM
ES14	70.93	MTM	65.89	AM	61.36	AM	66.06	MTM
ES15	60.52	AM	73.07	MTM	59.76	AM	64.45	AM
ES16	60.95	AM	60.71	AM	69.48	MTM	63.71	AM
ES17	60	AM	59.86	AM	59.41	AM	59.76	AM
OVERALL MEAN							66.02	MTM

Legend: VI (Verbal Interpretation) M-Mastered (96%-100), CAM-Closely approximating Mastery (86% - 95%), MTM-Moving Towards Mastery (66% - 85%), AM-Average Mastery (35% - 65%), LM-Low Mastery (16% - 34%), VL-Very Low Mastery (5% - 15%), NM-No Mastery (0% - 4%)

Table 10

Relationship between the RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers and Performance of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of SBM.

VARIABLES	School Year		School Year		School Year		AVG	VI	R	P-value	VI
	2020-2021		2021-2022		2022-2023						
	MEAN	VI	MEAN	VI	MEAN	VI					
Teacher's performance	4.34	VS	4.43	VS	4.48	VS	4.417	VS	0.986	0.104	NS
School's performance (SBM)	1.41	D	1.45	D	1.49	D	1.45	D			

Legend: VS (Very Satisfactory), D (Developing), VI (Verbal Interpretation), AVG (average), r (correlation coefficient), NS (Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Table 11

Relationship between the RPMS-PPST Based Performance of Teachers and Performance of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of MPS

Variables	School Year		School Year		School Year		AVG	VI	r	p-value	VI
	2020-2021		2021-2022		2022-2023						
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI					
Teacher's performance	4.34	VS	4.43	VS	4.48	VS	4.417	VS	0.970	0.156	NS
School's performance (MPS)	67.89	MTM	69.13	MTM	70.78	MTM	59.27	MTM			

Legend: VS (Very Satisfactory), D (Developing), VI (Verbal Interpretation), AVG (average), r (correlation coefficient), NS (Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the performance of teachers on IPCRF in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the three objectives. It is revealed that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.365. This suggests that teachers are meeting, or they even exceed the expectations of the quality of delivering content in the lessons. This likely indicates the teacher's proficiency in integrating different subject areas to provide a holistic educational experience for students (Smith, 2018). In this domain, the teacher makes sure that content knowledge can be integrated within or across curriculum teaching areas, ensures the positive use of ICT to facilitate learning, and applies a range of teaching strategies to develop thinking skills.

Table 2 presents the performance of teachers on IPCRF in terms of learning environment across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the three objectives. It is revealed that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.381. This indicates that teachers are still at their best in maintaining the classroom as a conducive learning place for learners. According to research by Smith et al. (2019), personalized approaches to teaching are crucial for addressing diverse educational needs, which can significantly enhance student engagement and success. This includes making the place safe for children, providing them with enough space, and well-lighted and ventilated areas and learning materials or resources are readily available in the classroom.

Table 3 reveals the performance of teachers on IPCRF in terms of diversity of learners across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the three objectives. It shows that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.488. This result indicates that teachers are very open-minded about the uniqueness of every learner in the classroom. They consider these individualities in the planning and implementation of the curriculum which allows learners to feel free and express their strengths and weaknesses. This proficiency is crucial for educators to tailor instruction according to the needs and progress of individual learners, thereby fostering personalized learning experiences (Smith, 2019).

Table 4 depicts the performance of teachers on IPCRF in terms of curriculum and planning across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the two objectives. It shows that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.275. This means that teachers perform well in preparing the lessons in the class. This includes lesson planning, preparing the materials for the lessons, and the alignment of the objectives to the stated curriculum. This result underscores the significance of employing diverse and suitable resources, including technology, to support and enhance the teaching-learning process, aligning with contemporary educational practices (Harris & Hofer, 2011).

Table 5 provides teachers' performance on IPCRF in terms of assessment and reporting across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the three objectives. The result reveals that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.398. This indicates that teachers are proficient in the design of assessments and in reporting to stakeholders. This is observable through the assessment made by teachers in the summative and formative assessments. Teachers also conduct quarterly reports to the parents as to how the learners perform in a quarter. This could indicate a strong emphasis on data-driven decision-making and personalized learning approaches within the educational context, as educators prioritize the use of data to tailor instruction and support individual student needs (Jones & Egley, 2019).

Table 6 presents teachers' performance on IPCRF in terms of community linkages and professional engagement across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021,

2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the three objectives. The data indicates that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.289. This suggests that educators are actively involved in building relationships with parents, guardians, and the wider school community, participating in professional networks, and engaging in reflective practices for ongoing professional development. According to Vescio, Ross, and Adams (2008), participation in professional networks can significantly contribute to teacher development by providing opportunities for sharing best practices, receiving feedback, and staying updated with current trends in education.

Table 7 reveals the performance of teachers on IPCRF in terms of personal growth and professional development across the three consecutive school years of 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023 based on the two objectives. The result indicates that the overall performance of teachers is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.467. This suggests that teachers proactively engage in activities where they uplift their careers professionally. These activities could be seminars, workshops, pursuing graduate studies, conferences, and other learning sessions to further integrate new teaching methodologies. Literature underscores the importance of adopting learner-centered approaches in teaching, emphasizing its positive impact on student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes (Nilson, 2016).

Table 8 provides the result of the school performance of selected public elementary in the third Congressional District of Quezon based on SBM (School-Based Management) for the three consecutive school years from 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023. Overall, the result of the study describes the performance of schools as developing in terms of level of practice with an overall mean of 1.49. This means that school respondents are in level 1 which, based on SBM, indicates that these schools are establishing frameworks and procedures that influence learning objectives and allow for a reasonable degree of community involvement. The overall rating could point to a slow but steady improvement in the efficiency of SBM implementation, or it could suggest that stakeholders have become more familiar with and accustomed to SBM principles over time. These schools could focus on strengthening their leadership capacity by providing continuous professional development opportunities for school leaders and administrators (Harris, 2008). Moreover, fostering a culture of trust and collaboration among staff members and stakeholders is crucial for successful SBM implementation (MacBeath & Dempster, 2008). By prioritizing transparent communication and shared decision-making processes, these schools can work towards improving their SBM practices.

Table 9 presents the result of the school performance of selected public elementary in the third Congressional District of Quezon based on MPS (Mean Percentage Score) for the three consecutive school years from 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023. The overall mean of 66.02 is described as moving towards mastery (MTM). This suggests that the school is moving in the right direction in terms of increasing the learning mastery levels of its learners. It also indicates the effective strategies of schools in the delivery of lessons, implementing interventions for different learning areas, and enhancement of curriculum over the three-school year period. According to Hattie (2009), effective instructional strategies, such as feedback, teacher-student relationships,

and classroom management, significantly impact student achievement. These schools might be employing such strategies to enhance student learning and performance.

Table 10 reveals the results of the relationship between the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers and the performance of selected public elementary schools in the third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of SBM (School-Based Management) for the three consecutive school years from 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023. The obtained data show that there is no significant relationship between the teacher's performance and the school's performance in terms of SBM with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.986 and p -value of 0.104 at a 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is a strong positive relationship between two variables but indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant. This finding is aligned with previous studies which indicate several factors can be the reason for its weak association such as school leadership, school resources, and the student's demographics which also have impact in the overall performance of the school (Alvarez & Agbayani, 2007). While there is a strong positive association between teachers and school performance, the teacher's role plays a vital meaning in developing learners' academic performance which greatly contributes to the overall school performance. The continuous assessment and development of teachers professionally through RPMS-PPST impacts the quality of teaching and affects the quality of learning. Like the findings of Lim (2020), a teacher who constructively receives feedback that develops professionally can have higher self-efficacy, which is correlated with improved student performance.

Table 11 presents the results of the relationship between the RPMS-PPST-based performance of teachers and the performance of selected public elementary schools in the third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of MPS (Mean Percentage Score) for the three consecutive school years from 2020-2021, 2021-2022, and 2022-2023. The data reveal that there is no significant relationship between the teacher's performance and the school's performance in terms of MPS with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.970 and p -value of 0.156 at a 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables but there is not enough evidence to conclude that it is statistically significant. Despite the indicative result of the study which show less evidence to support the significant relationship between the teacher's performance and school performance, Puyot (2017) believes that the relationship of the RPMS-PPST and school performance lies in their shared objective which aims to enhance the quality of education and the performance of students through the effective management and accountability of the school and stakeholders, including teachers. This could mean that aligning the performance of teachers and allowing schools to have greater autonomy in terms of decision-making, initiating programs and projects for the teachers, and learners can ensure quality of learning outcomes.

The study reveals that teachers performed satisfactorily in the RMPS-PPST indicators during the previous school years 2020-2021 to 2022-2023. However, school performance in terms of SBM level of practice showed a developing level, while in terms of school MPS, they are moving towards mastery. The study suggests developing an intervention to enhance school performance in terms of MPS and SBM level of practice

by equipping teachers with effective pedagogical strategies and empowering school administrators and staff with the necessary skills. The intervention program targets teacher across all grade levels and subjects, as well as school administrators, including principals and department heads in the third congressional district of Quezon. The three-day training workshop will include interactive lectures, group discussions, case studies, roleplaying activities, hands-on workshops, peer learning, and sharing sessions. The participants are expected to enhance pedagogical skills, strengthen school administrators' capacity to implement SBM practices, foster a culture of shared leadership and accountability, and increase collaboration among staff members.

Conclusions

This descriptive correlational study aimed to determine the relationship between the RPMS-PSST based performance of teachers and performance of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The performance of teachers based on RPMS-PPST and its seven domains and the performance of public elementary schools in terms of School-Based Management (SBM) and Mean Percentage Score (MPS) were determined and the relationship of the two variables were evaluated for significance.

The performance of teachers based on the RPMS-PPST domains is described as very satisfactory, indicating that teachers are consistently meeting and exceeding the expectations across all the domains, demonstrating a high level of competence and effectiveness in the teaching process. On the other hand, the performance of public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon is described as developing in terms of SBM level of practice, implying that schools are gradually adopting policies and practices aligned with SBM principles. While the school performance in terms of MPS is described as moving towards mastery, suggesting that student's performance in terms of academic assessment is improving and approaching the desired level of mastery.

There is no significant relationship between the RPMS-PPST based performance of teachers and performance of public elementary schools in terms of SBM in the third congressional district of Quezon. This means that the two variables are not statistically significant. Likewise, there is no significant relationship between the RPMS-PPST based performance of teachers and performance of public elementary schools in the third congressional district of Quezon in terms of MPS. This means that there is not enough evidence to support the claim. Therefore, the null hypothesis of the study claiming that there is no significant relationship between the variables is accepted. In connection to the results, an intervention program is developed to enhance the knowledge and skills of teachers, school administrators and staff in terms of MPS and SBM to improve school performance.

Recommendations

The findings of the study in terms of the teacher's performance based on RPMS-PPST is at a very satisfactory level. It is being suggested that teachers may continue to be more engaged in professional development programs or learning sessions where topics are focused on ICT use, learner-centered strategies, communication with stakeholders, assessment methods, and philosophies of teaching. Participating in collaborative activities such as seminars, workshops, and conferences would allow them to share best practices and grow professionally and sustainably. Since the results of the study reveal that majority of the schools are in the developing level of practice in SBM, schools in maturing level may benchmark or share their best practices to developing school in terms of SBM implementation. This will provide collaboration for schools in uplifting their performances. The result of the study shows that half of the school respondents are in average mastery in terms of school performance based on MPS. The study suggests that schools may utilize this data to promote data-driven decision-making approach in the assessment and evaluation of learning outcomes. They may partner with other schools who performed better in terms of MPS to gain higher mastery level.

This study is limited only in determining the performance of teachers based on RPMS-PPST and the school performance in terms of SBM and MPS, as well as the relationship between the two variables. Further study may be conducted to explore additional variables that may impact the performance of schools. Based on literature, factors such as resources, community involvement, and student demographics could be considered to give a more comprehensive understanding of the school performance. The overall findings of the study suggested that teachers continuously engage in professional development activities to enhance knowledge and skills that impact school performance. Based on this result, the researcher developed an intervention which schools may adapt or modify.

Considering the limitation of this study, future researchers may conduct similar study using other measures of school performance and other locale with longer period of school years to be analyzed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study focused on the performance of teachers and the school emphasizes the importance of ethical standards. It requires informed consent from all participants, confidentiality, and anonymity to protect their privacy. Objectivity and integrity are crucial, with researcher minimizing bias in data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The researcher used rigorous methodologies, validated assessment tools, and report findings transparently. Prioritizing the welfare and rights of participants which is also essential, ensuring minimal risk and potential benefits to the educational community. The researcher respects cultural sensitivities and diversity of the population. By upholding these ethical standards, this research aims to contribute to the development of effective

intervention programs aimed at enhancing teacher performance and overall educational outcomes.

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